

DIGITAL INDIA MISSION: REVOLUTIONISING OPEN DATA MECHANISMS SINCE 2015

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1. Introduction

Open Data Mechanism in India involves the usage of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in governance. It adjudicates for SMART governance which implies Simple, Moral, Accountable, Responsive and Transparent, better known as E-Governance for adopting a citizen-centric approach, improving the quality and delivery of public services. E-Governance has proved to be cost-effective, inclusive, holistic, easy and reliable. The National E-Governance Plan (NeGP) was approved in 2006 with short-term goals, the scope of which were further expanded in 2011 with a lot of schemes and initiatives in Health, Education, Public Distribution System (PDS), Security, Human Resources Development, Enterprise Architecture, Banks and Post-Offices.

The paper shall explain the paradigm shift in India's electronic and digital revolution in its open and transparent data mechanism since 1990s. It will also discuss the schemes and initiatives of the Indian government both at the national and regional level to ensure transparency and accountability. It shall explain, in detail, the achievements and challenges of the Digital India Mission in the past seven years in general, and the different initiatives in particular. Special attention shall be paid to its immense contribution in empowering the world's largest democracy. Finally, the paper will highlight the elaborate revolution that the Indian government has made globally and its contribution towards tackling the Covid-19 Pandemic.

2. Background

Launched by Prime Minister Shri Narendra Modi in 2015, the Digital India campaign, the Ministry of Electronics and Information Technology (MeitY), ensures the accessibility of government's services to the citizens on an online platform, improving their digital literacy and enhancing broadband connectivity (Ministry of electronics and Information Technology, Government of India, 2022). It also seeks to make the Indian economy a knowledge-centric and a digitally empowered one. The campaign involves Initiatives like Bharatmala, BharatNet, Make in India, Startup India, Standup India and Sagarmala.

The first Open Data Mechanism of India was launched in 2012 named as the National Data Sharing and Accessibility Policy (NDSAP) which formally conferred on the National Informatics Centre the responsibility of the Open Government Data Platform. The Open Government Data (OGD)

Platform of India is the sixth pillar (Information for All) under the Digital India Mission for the Central government departments and ministries to officially publish and update their data, statistics, catalogues, documents and applications in an open format for ensuring a responsible, accessible, innovative and transparent functioning of government within its framework through workshops, hackathons, Work-flow based Data Management systems, portals and application softwares. It also enables the citizens and stakeholders to express their views, suggestions and opinions on the different government policies and initiatives, conduct researches on them and seek clarification and explanation from the nodal officers at different levels of the government. A separate Community Portal (<https://community.data.gov.in>) acts as a platform to exchange ideas and share knowledge through blogs. The second phase of OGD, that is, OGD 2.0 is operative under the NITI Aayog as the National Data and Analytics Platform and under the Ministry of Housing and Urban Affairs (MoHUA) as the India Urban Data Exchange. In future, the improved environment for Open Data shall act as a critical enabler for boosting the nation's Artificial Intelligence Mechanism (Carmeli, 2021). The NDSAP has enabled wider accessibility of data and it is still working for the enhancement of wider data usability. The MeitY has published the Draft India Data Accessibility & Use Policy 2022 for the standardisation and establishment of metadata management framework for the improvement of quality and accessibility of non-personal government datasets which was further replaced by the Draft National Data Governance Framework Policy (Vats, 2022). After the launch of NDSAP, many academic circles, higher education institutions, governmental and civil society organisations have launched their own Open Data platforms, for example, the India Data Portal by the Indian School of Business and the Open Budgets India portal by the Centre for Budget and Governance Accountability. The use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) is prevalent in India's education, healthcare and agricultural spheres, for example, the Shodhganga contains all the Doctoral theses of the research scholars.

3. Platforms facilitating Open Data Mechanism

Rural and urban areas of India have been provided with broadband connectivity under the Broadband Highways initiative and Universal Access to Mobile Connectivity initiative. Common Service Centres and Post Offices for providing internet accessibility and delivering government and business services in Panchayats have been transformed into multi-service centres. The governance process in public and private offices, academic institutions, industries and banking institutions have been made transparent with the use of IT by online tracking, electronic database, online grievance redressal, online repositories, speedy service delivery and interface between the departments (Press Information Bureau, 2022). The mechanism of biometric attendance is mandatory in all institutions in India that provides a transparency in the maintenance of records of the absence and presence of the concerned people.

The major apps that have brought a transformation in India's Open Data Mechanisms are:

1. Startup India- Announced in 2015, the app serves as a platform to allow the startups develop a network in accessing free tools and resources and knowledge-sharing through workshops and programmes.
2. MyGov- The platform actively engages citizen participation in governance and adopts a bottom-up approach for strengthening the democracy.

3. UMANG serves as a single window portal/ application software for providing services to the citizens at all levels of government.
4. Aarogya Setu is a mobile application for providing essential and immediate health services to the people in combating Covid-19.
5. BHIM App is a mobile payment application software been created by the National Payments Corporation of India on the Unified Payments Interface (UPI) in the year 2016. It has helped in the promotion of cashless transactions by the facilitation of direct e-payments.
6. ENAM portal (Electronic National Agriculture Market) is a trading website that is supported by the Indian government to connect small grocery shops to develop a national market for agricultural products by making it easier for the farmers to remove the trade barriers and receive information about the prices, demand and supplies of their respective products on their smartphones.
7. Mausam App has been built by the Ministry of Earth Sciences, Government of India to observe and forecast weather changes and obtain radar photos.
8. Agrimarket Mobile App provides information about the prices of the crops to the farmers within 50 kilometres of their own device.
9. E-Kranti Mission has many Mission Mode Projects for the use of technology in education (Massive Open Online Courses), healthcare, farmers (online payments), mobile based energy services and disaster- related services, mobile banking, Micro-ATM Programme and post offices, online hearing of court proceedings and cyber security.
10. The PM SVANidhi App (Pradhan Mantri Street Vendors' Atmanirbhar Nidhi), launched by the Ministry of Housing and Urban Affairs, Government of India, incentivises digital transaction amongst the street vendors by providing them information about the affordable loans at cheaper interest rates by the governments to develop their businesses.
11. The Jaldoot App has been launched by the Ministry of Rural Development for measuring the groundwater levels twice a year, that is, once in pre-monsoon months and the other in post-monsoon months (NewsOnAIR, 2022).
12. Apps like the Electronic- Know Your Customer (e-KYC), the Electronic Document Storage System (DigiLocker) and the Electronic Signature System (eSign) were introduced to help businesses streamline their operations.

4. International Cooperation on Open Data Mechanisms

International cooperation in global digital policy between India and other countries is a potential research area. Recently, the Hon'ble Finance Minister of India Smt. Nirmala Sitharaman said that India's Open Network for Digital Commerce has revolutionised the retail and manufacturing sector and envisioned plenty of scope for collaboration in the digital sector between India and the United States. The federal government was engaged with foreign investors to ease rules for more investments. She also said the country was confident of handling the challenge of high inflation and that its economic revival was driven by government reforms.

Cooperation in global digital policy is considered one of the most promising fields in the strategic partnership between India and the European Union (EU). However, profound differences are apparent in terms of implementation, for example with regard to data protection, competences of security authorities and the future global digital order. Meanwhile, similar problems are being addressed in the EU's negotiations with the US on digital trade issues. Possible compromises there

could also form components of an understanding with India. Shared democratic values are consistently referred to as a justification for efforts to strengthen Europe's cooperation with India. In their Roadmap 2025, India and the EU affirm their interest in promoting an "open, free, stable and secure cyber-space" and fighting cybercrime. But the road to this goal is proving to be rocky (Voelson and Wagner, 2022). They are willing to cooperate in areas like an open, free, stable and secure cyberspace and cyber security, ICT cooperation under the India-EU Joint Working Group on sustainable digital infrastructure, services, norms and regulatory frameworks, ensuring interoperability of networks, promoting international standards of data protection, quantum computing, artificial intelligence, agritech, healthtech and blockchain.

Recently India, the EU and nine countries signed the "Joint Declaration on Privacy and the Protection of Personal Data: Strengthening Trust in the Digital Environment" for fostering international cooperation to promote high data protection and privacy standards based on certain core elements increasingly shared across the Indo-Pacific region, Europe and beyond. The European Union, Australia, Comoros, India, Japan, Mauritius, New Zealand, South Korea, Singapore and Sri Lanka said rapid technological developments, in particular in information and digital technologies, have brought benefits for their economies and societies, as well as new challenges for privacy and the protection of personal data.

5. Achievements and Challenges

One of the biggest achievements of India's Open Data Mechanism is that it has led to greater accessibility and transparency of government's digital services to the citizens. An umbrella programme covering innumerable initiatives and schemes under the MeitY, the UPI initiative has flourished the businesses of street vendors to business tycoons. It has helped in connecting the citizens with more than 300 public services. The Digital India campaign with Digital Village brought into reality the concept of a traditional India into a modern, tech-savvy one. Speed was achieved in the affairs of the government and private businesses. Public information has become readily accessible in your fingers. For this, it has provided high-quality internet connectivity in 2.5 lakh villages and lowered the data tariffs (Chaturvedi, 2021). The role of CivicDataLab in the skill enhancement of the government officials in finance and accounting sectors is commendable.

The performance of the Open Data Mechanism in India in the fields of healthcare, trade and commerce, banking, agriculture, education and research, smart cities projects and mobility has been splendid. A more synchronised database management between the central and state governments is needed since India has a vast diverse population. For a diverse country, data collection, editing, tabulation and making it digitally transparent becomes a Herculean task. More hackathons, educational and training programmes, capacity-building workshops with skilled data contributors and resource persons are needed for the spread of digital literacy among the citizens and also for the upgradation of the existing database to higher quality and higher value ones (Vats, 2022). The collective participation of civil society, government and industry is needed for a more dynamic, spontaneous and open artificial intelligence mechanism in governance and benefitting the Indian corporations and startups. An Open Data legislation is the need of the hour that lends uniformity and robustness for the careful selection of datasets and their expansion to state governments. More involvement of researchers, academia, IT professionals and data managers is required to meet the rising demands of Open Data. A uniform Personal Data Protection legislation is also needed for

safeguarding the privacy, security and rights of individuals in case of anonymised data (Neufeld, 2021).

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